

ISic3634

I.Sicily inscription 3634

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2006-04; 2018-07-05

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Haluntium

Place of origin (modern)

San Marco d'Alunzio

Provenance

fr.1 recovered from campanile of Cattedrale di S. Nicola di Bari; fr.2 found in the external wall of the apse of the chiesa di Tutti i Santi

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, S. Marco d'Alunzio, Museo della cultura e delle Arti Figurative
Bizantine e Normanne

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 58 cm

Width 67 cm

Depth 43 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Augusto

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491405

EDCS 23900186

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques*

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Manganaro, G. 1965. Ricerche di antichità e di epigrafia siceliote. *Archeologia Classica*. 17: 183-210. At 201 tav.71.3

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 48 n.235

Bonanno, C. 1997-1998. Scavi e indagini nel territorio di Caronia e San Marco d'Alunzio. *Kokalos*. 43-44: 423-451. At 447 tav.107.1

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